

Risk Factors Associated with the Development and Progression of Chronic Kidney Disease in Patients Attending UMF 35

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 24 February 2026	Objective: To analyze the modifiable risk factors associated with the onset and progression of chronic kidney disease in patients at UMF 35. Materials and Methods: An analytical, prospective, observational, and cross-sectional study was conducted. Data were collected using a researcher-designed instrument specifically developed for this study. Descriptive statistics were used for qualitative variables, including absolute frequencies and percentages. Pearson's chi-square (χ^2) test was applied, considering a statistically significant difference at $p < 0.005$. Results: A total of 280 patients were included; 149 (53.2%) were women, with a mean age of 70.34 years. A statistically significant correlation was found between abdominal circumference and a glomerular filtration rate of less than 30 mL/min/1.73 m ² , with an incidence of 42 out of 121 cases and a relative risk (RR) of 1.393 (95% CI: 1.055–1.838).
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I. INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) has become a global public health priority due to the increase in its prevalence observed over recent decades. According to Argaiz et al.,¹ the estimated prevalence of CKD in Mexico in 2021 was 9,184.9 per 100,000 inhabitants, with Mexico City being the entity with the highest number of reported cases.

Several authors have focused on studying the presence of risk factors (RFs) associated with this disease. These may be classified as modifiable, including obesity, smoking, dyslipidemia, and metabolic syndrome, and non-modifiable factors, such as type 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic arterial hypertension.² In addition, other RFs have been identified, including elevated uric acid levels, increased body mass index (BMI),³ consumption of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs),⁴ and abdominal circumference.⁵

Daily water intake is considered a renal protective factor, as is engagement in regular physical activity.⁶

This topic has been a research priority for several decades; in 2003, a study was conducted comparing insulin resistance, central obesity, dyslipidemia, and glycated hemoglobin levels with the risk of developing CKD.⁷

Although the presence of comorbidities such as type 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic arterial hypertension is considered a non-modifiable factor, as these are chronic and incurable diseases, they can be controlled; therefore, they may be regarded as potentially modifiable factors.⁸

There is no unified method to define the progression of CKD; however, it may be considered progressive when there is a decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of >5 mL/min/1.73 m² per year, or a decrease in GFR of >10 mL/min/1.73 m² over a five-year period.

Likewise, progression is considered present when the patient transitions to a more advanced or severe category according to the criteria established by the KDIGO guidelines, either based on estimated GFR or albuminuria levels.^{9,10}

The objective of this study was to determine the presence of previously identified RFs for the development of this pathology and to demonstrate the association between these RFs and the degree of CKD observed in the study population.

II. METHODS

An observational, cross-sectional, retrospective, and analytical study was conducted. A questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose was developed to collect the

necessary information for the study, and an informed consent form was prepared. This research was approved by the corresponding ethics committee.

Subsequently, beneficiaries registered at Family Medicine Unit (FMU) No. 35 with a diagnosis of chronic kidney disease (CKD) were selected. To determine the sample size, the finite population formula was used, resulting in a total of 280 participants, selected through non-probability convenience sampling.

All individuals aged 18 years or older who agreed to participate in the study, signed the informed consent form, and received medical follow-up at FMU 35 were included.

During the interview, the principal investigator read the questions aloud to the study participants and recorded their responses on the specifically designed form. Upon completion of the interview, the researchers proceeded to retrieve complementary clinical information from the patients' medical records.

Once the data were obtained, a unique identification code was assigned to each patient in order to ensure data confidentiality. The information was then entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet for subsequent statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

Descriptive statistics were applied using measures of central tendency (mean) and dispersion (maximum, minimum, range, variance, and standard deviation). For qualitative variables, absolute frequencies and percentages were calculated. Bivariate analysis was performed using Pearson's chi-square (χ^2) test with a 95% confidence interval (CI), and relative risk (RR) was used to assess the strength of association for statistically significant findings.

III. RESULTS

A total of 280 patients with a diagnosis of chronic kidney disease (CKD), corresponding to KDIGO stages 3, 4, and 5, were included in this study. All participants completed a specifically designed questionnaire developed by the principal investigator, based on the main modifiable risk factors identified in the literature review.

Of the 280 participants, 149 (53.2%) were women. The mean age was 70.34 years (range: 31–90 years), with a standard deviation of 12.039. Regarding sociodemographic characteristics, marital status was reported as follows: 76 participants (27.1%) were married, 72 (25.7%) were in a domestic partnership, 57 (20.4%) were widowed, 39 (13.9%) were single, and 36 (12.9%) were divorced.

In terms of educational level, 96 participants (34.3%) had completed upper secondary education, 93 (33.2%) had completed secondary education, 50 (17.9%) had completed primary education, 31 (11.1%) held a bachelor's degree, 8 (2.9%) had no formal education, and 2 (0.7%) had completed postgraduate studies.

A total of 226 participants (80.7%) had a diagnosis of type 1 or type 2 diabetes mellitus; of these, 147 (52.5%) reported the use of pharmacological treatment for disease control. Additionally, 227 participants (81.1%) had a diagnosis of chronic arterial hypertension, and 141 (50.4%) reported receiving antihypertensive treatment.

Regarding CKD duration, 89 participants (31.8%) had been diagnosed for 1–5 years, 69 (24.6%) for 5–10 years, 63 (22.5%) for more than 10 years, and 59 (21.1%) for less than one year. At the time of diagnosis, 116 participants (41.4%) were classified as CKD stage 3a, 88 (31.4%) as stage 3b, 44 (15.7%) as stage 4, and 31 (11.1%) as stage 5.

Most participants, 215 (76.8%), reported not engaging in regular physical activity. Additionally, 142 participants (50.7%) reported current or prior consumption of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) for more than three years. A total of 150 participants (53.4%) reported consuming less than 2 liters of drinking water per day. Likewise, 135 participants (48.2%) reported current or previous smoking for five or more years, with a consumption of at least 20 cigarettes per day.

IV. DISCUSSION

For several years, the high prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in the Latin American population has been well recognized, with this region showing the highest median prevalence compared to other regions worldwide. Mexico ranks among the top three countries most affected by this pathology; therefore, it is expected that the risk factors (RFs) associated with the development of CKD have been extensively studied. Among these, the main associated factors have been the presence of diabetes mellitus, chronic arterial hypertension, and overweight/obesity.¹¹

In a study conducted in Colombia and published in 2024, an association was found between CKD progression and female sex, age over 60 years, elevated serum creatinine levels, and the presence of albuminuria. The investigators also evaluated other RFs similar to those considered in the present study, including abdominal circumference, smoking status, BMI, dyslipidemia, presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), chronic arterial hypertension, and CKD stage. When comparing results, although no statistically significant association with female sex was observed in our study, our study population was predominantly composed of women.

Another study conducted in Cuba and published in 2019 found that the main RFs associated with CKD were the presence of diabetes mellitus, chronic arterial hypertension, and a family history of the disease. Smoking, hypercholesterolemia, and age over 60 years doubled the risk of developing CKD. Although no statistically significant association with these factors was found in our study, up to 50% of patients presented at least one of these

RFs, and approximately 80% had either diabetes or hypertension.

In the present study, a statistically significant association was found between chronic NSAID consumption and abdominal circumference as predisposing RFs for the development or progression of CKD. This finding represents a strength of the study, as it demonstrates that although the traditionally recognized RFs are important, other RFs should not be overlooked, and a culture of prevention should be actively promoted.

The strengths of this study include its application in a Mexican population. Limitations include the relatively small sample size and the lack of longitudinal follow-up of participants.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this study was to determine the presence of risk factors associated with the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in the population attending Family Medicine Unit (FMU) No. 35, in order to initiate the implementation of actions aimed at preventing or reducing the presence of these factors. It is important to highlight that there is currently no validated instrument to assess the risk profile of these patients; therefore, future research should focus on the development of a tool that is useful, practical, and easy to apply, in order to promote awareness of modifiable factors that can be addressed at the primary care level to prevent the development of this highly costly and disabling disease, which significantly impairs not only patients' quality of life but also that of their families and social environment.

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